

Key Concepts: Happiness Control System of a Human

Introduction

Happiness looks analogical to temperature (Harari). Hence the term happiness control like temperature control. The objective is to model the happiness control system (HCS) of a human. The purpose is that the model is abstract so it can be used across boundaries. The model can accommodate momentarily happiness control and extended happiness control that requires complex planning or happiness control in progress. Hypothesis of significance of the work is significance for the field psychiatry and the field philosophy of action. One figurative example of part of the model is the scene networking in the movie *Bridget Jones' Diary* at time 00:18:38 till 00:19:27. It shows the fastness of the model, e.g. how fast Bridget can observe the result of introducing people with thoughtful details by saying prick, does not settle with it and does settle with another result instead. Future-directed intentions have for Bratman at least two important functions in deliberation: they have a settling function and a coordination function (SEP). Alvarez argues that the power to act is a two-way power: a power to either do or not do something (SEP).

The model

The model of the HCS of a human is heptalistic and hierarchical (fig. 1). The model can be one-line, e.g. example 1-3, or multiple-line, e.g. example 4 (fig. 2). It is unclear whether there is a maximum of lines. Concepts like consciousness and awareness could be possible practical aspects for () and + to establish the model, where + could be cross dimensional wiring and () could be activity and passivity. Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy states: "There is an important difference between activity and passivity: the fire is active with respect to the log when it burns it (and the log passive with respect to the fire)." (SEP). The first sum of the model of HCS of a human is ()_ontic plus ()_ontological which makes ()_happystat. Camus reports that deciding whether or not life is worth living is to answer the fundamental question in philosophy (SEP). This is the ontological differentiation designated by Heidegger. Ontic and ontological are explained by Vorstenbosch in the book *De Overtocht* which won de Van Helldingenprijs in 2023.

"There are thus two domains, for which Sass comes to use the words 'ontic' and 'ontological,' which are precisely the two words with which Heidegger designates the so-called ontological differentiation. 'Ontic' relates to the things (the Being) that exist in the everyday world, while 'ontological' refers to something larger or overarching, something we might call 'beingness.' In philosophy, these two frames of thought are often confused, Heidegger says. In Descartes' cogito, for example, the 'I think' - itself a mundane, 'ontological' event - is postulated as bearing ground for all of reality." (Vorstenbosch, p 70).

The mechanism of the ontological differentiation is that ()_ontological is the Boolean value about ()_ontic. ()_ontological measures if ()_ontic is true. If ()_ontic is true, then ()_ontic is true. If else, then ()_ontic is false. ()_ontological does not measure if ()_ontic is false, because it is impossible to measure false. Parmenides states it is impossible to measure non beingness (Störig). Non beingness is a synonym of false. There are two priority based targets of ()_happystat: true, work and play break-even. When ()_ontic is false, then ()_happystat wants to make it true. When ()_ontic is true, then ()_happystat wants to make it work or play. Oxytocin, serotonin and dopamine could resemble: to make true, to make work, to make play. Work and play appears in leading techincubator YES!Delft in Europe where "work hard, play

hard” is a saying in the culture (De Ingenieur). The second sum of the model of HCS of a human is ()_happystat plus ()_memory which makes ()_dream. The third sum of the model of HCS of a human is ()_dream plus ()_navigation which makes ()_dreamstat. A TomTom is a navigation device which offers different routes like shortest, fastest, economical, et cetera (TomTom). ()_navigation is a navigation device which offers the routes: shortest, automatic, socially accepted. The target of ()_dreamstat is one hundred per cent. The fourth sum of the model of HCS of a human is that of ()_dreamstat and ()_x. ()_x is nonhuman or another human.

Future work

Future work could be a convene of psychiatrists to manipulate the model so as an ill HCS of a human occurs. Furthermore, veterinarians could convene to manipulate the model so as the HCS of an ape occurs. Furthermore, philosophers of action and physicists could convene on the distinguishment: work, play, action. Arendt distinguishes three: labour, work (the Aristotelian poíêsis), and action (the Aristotelian praxis) (SEP).

Figure 1: The model of the happiness control system of a human

$$(((\text{()_ontic} + \text{()_ontological})_happystat + \text{()_memory})_dream + \text{()_navigation})_dreamstat + \text{()_x}$$

Figure 2: Examples of the model of the happiness control system of a human

Example 1

Sum 1: (I pass the school year)_ontic + (false)_ontological = (<true)_happystat

Sum 2: (<true)_happystat + (I did not study for the exam)_memory = (study for the exam)_dream

Sum 3: (study for the exam)_dream + (study in the library)_navigation = (56%)_dreamstat

Sum 4: (56%)_dreamstat + (library/study book)_x

Example 2

Sum 1: (I pass the school year)_ontic + (true)_ontological = (work>play)_happystat

Sum 2: (work>play)_happystat + (there is a swimming pool close by)_memory = (visit the swimming pool)_dream

Sum 3: (visit swimming pool)_dream + (wear pink swimming shorts)_navigation = (90%)_dreamstat

Sum 4: (90%)_dreamstat + (pink swimming shorts/swimming pool)_x

Example 3

Sum 1: (I pass the school year)_ontic + (true)_ontological = (work<play)_happystat

Sum 2: (work<play)_happystat + (there are other courses available)_memory = (take an additional course)_dream

Sum 3: (take an additional course)_dream + (sneak into college for free)_navigation = (10%)_dreamstat

Sum 4: (10%)_dreamstat + (college/note book)_x

Example 4

Sum 1: (I pass the school year)_ontic + (true)_ontological = (work<play)_happystat

Sum 2: (work<play)_happystat + (there are other courses available)_memory = (take an additional course)_dream

Sum 3: (take an additional course)_dream + (

Sum 1: (sneak into college for free)_ontic + (false)_ontological = (<true)_happystat

Sum 2: (<true)_happystat + (the back row gets little attention)_memory = (sit in the back row)_dream

Sum 3: (sit in the back row)_dream + (arrive early when it is a little crowded)_navigation = (5%)_dreamstat

Sum 4: (5%)_dreamstat + (wristwatch/other students)_x

)_navigation = (10%)_dreamstat

Sum 4: (10%)_dreamstat + (college/note book)_x

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